

JURISPRUDENCE

FEATURES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF INFORMATION CRIMES IN AZERBAIJAN CRIMINAL LAW

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Abstract

As in any field, there are disadvantages to the development of technology. In the last decades of the twentieth century, as a result of the progressive development of technology, significant changes have been observed in the state and dynamics of crime worldwide. Thus, new crimes have emerged and expanded in the digital and virtual spheres, creating legal threats to people's lives.

These violations, defined as crimes, are in theory "computer crimes", "computer-related crimes", "electronic crimes", "digital crimes", "high-tech crimes", "information crimes", "cybercrime" and so on. is called.

For this reason, in the article, the criminal composition of information crimes was investigated in more detail and the object and objective aspects of acts considered information crime according to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan as a socially dangerous act were studied.

Keywords: cybercrime, cyber security, computer system, information, information security, data base

The crime is defined as a socially hazardous conduct when it comprises of a collection of objective and subjective characteristics established in the law. The following four factors make up the crime's objective and subjective characteristics: 1) the crime's purpose; 2) the crime's objective aspect; 3) the crime's subject; and 4) the crime's subjective aspect.

When it comes to the crime's goal, it's worth noting that criminal law divides scientific crime into three categories: 1) the crime's broad objective; 2) the crime's particular purpose; 3) the crime's immediate object;

The attribute that immediately characterizes the thing is always within the scope of the crime among the objects specified above. As a result, in order to solve the problem, the object must be specified explicitly.

The appearance of a socially harmful aim that occurred at a certain time and place, under specific circumstances, and that impacted existing public relations is an objective indicator of a crime[3].

The objective part of a crime, according to another definition, is the outward nature of a socially harmful act or inaction that hurts or threatens to harm the target of the crime defined by law, as well as the conditions in which the harm was done[5]. In addition to socially harmful acts and their corresponding socially dangerous results, the objective part of the crime also includes the causal link between the socially harmful behavior, the socially dangerous effects, the technique of committing the crime, the tools and equipment used, and the location, time, and conditions in which it happened.

In light of the foregoing, the objective characteristics of the crime can be classified as follows: 1) an intentional act or omission; 2) a potentially harmful societal effect; 3) the causal link between action (inaction) and consequence; 4) the manner of committing the verb; 5) the location and time of the conduct; 6) the

conditions of the act; 7) the tools and methods used in the commission of the law[5].

A criminal conduct must include a socially hazardous act or omission. Other elements are optional, meaning they are not required to be included in every offense.

The crime's target is public relations, which is protected by law.

The general objective of "Cyber Crimes" is public relations and data protection using computer technologies. The nature of each of the offences listed in Chapter 30 of the Criminal Code distinguishes its intent in addition to its general purpose.

The objective aspects of cybercrime can be clarified using the criteria listed above.

Article 271 of the Criminal Code defines the offense of unauthorized access to a computer system. Before identifying the plot's aim and objective, it's important to remember that the computer is an electronic calculator that stores data and performs mathematical, logical, and other calculations[1]. As a result, the thing in issue is data for the purpose of creating computer data.

The offense in question concerns public relations issues that develop during the safeguarding of computer systems and data. The inviolability and integrity of legally protected information, as well as the property and other rights of the information's legal owners, are direct targets of individual, societal, and governmental security. In this scenario, a person who joins the computer system without authorization is infringing on the computer system and the information to which he has no access. This data is the damage object in this case.

The information and data immediately on the computer are the target of the crime. It's also worth noting that, unlike the criminal, the subject is a component of the caste object.

The breach of security measures in a computer system or any portion of it, the seizure of computer information stored there, or any other personal goal is the objective side of the crime of unauthorized access to a computer system.

In the context of breaches in this area, clarifying the objective nature of the crime in detail aids in determining the breadth of the crime by unlawfully accessing a computer system.

The nature of this illegal crime indicates that it is a socially hazardous act, as may be deduced from its character. Illegal access to information also involves gaining access to information through the unauthorized use of acceptable technological equipment[4].

In this scenario, it's important to remember that the computer system and data must be in excellent functioning order for the conduct to be regarded criminal. It is not a question of whether or not the computer system and its data are accessible and useable as a whole, but rather whether or not the computer system has been hacked[4].

Another situation to be determined is whether computer data is protected in accordance with the Republic of Azerbaijan's relevant legal regulations as a result of illegal and unauthorized access to this information, and whether the state's, the owner's, the author's, or other legal and natural persons' rights are violated.

The unlawfully accessed computer system and data must infringe the rights of the owner of the computer system or any natural or legal person for an act to fall under the scope of Article 271 of the Criminal Code.

Article 271 of the Criminal Code defines the act of accessing a computer system or any part of it for the purpose of obtaining computer data, regardless of whether the information is of personal, public, or government importance, and whether it is partially or completely compromised as a result of the access.

Without the right to illegally enter a computer system or any portion of it, the crime is committed. This includes anybody who does not have the legal authority to do so, such as someone who is not a valid user, whose right is restricted by law, or who lacks the necessary license.

As previously stated, the Criminal Code's Note to Article 271 defines "computer system" quite explicitly. The idea of "any portion of the computer system," on the other hand, is not defined in the code. To me, every portion of a computer system that contains information significant to its owner or any human or legal body is a part of a computer system. Illegal access to a section of a computer system by a person who does not have the authority to do so is punishable under Article 271 of the Penal Code.

It is a violation of security measures in a computer system or any portion of it, including the interception of computer information stored therein, or any other personal aim, according to article 271. These features represent the action's subjective traits, which will be examined more below.

The following are the key elements of the crime of unauthorized access to a computer system: 1) the individual has the right to access; 2) the security measures are violated.

The unauthorized seizure of computer data is another felony under this section of the Criminal Code. Article 272 of the Criminal Code specifies the elements of this offense.

Following the Republic of Azerbaijan's acceptance of the European Convention on Cybercrime, this article was added to the Criminal Code.

The crime described in this article has a distinct and extra goal. It governs public relations as a private item, ensuring that diverse data flowing in the computer system, as well as the bearers of this data, are protected from electromagnetic radiation. Additional objectives, property relationships, people's constitutional rights and freedoms, and relationships governing the regular operation of governmental organizations, among others.

Computer data and the electromagnetic radiation of computer systems that transmit this data are the topic of the alleged crime.

Non-public computer data communicated from, to, or via a computer system, as well as the intentional capture of electromagnetic radiation by computer systems conveying such computer data by a person who does not have the right to it, using technological methods.

Information that only certain persons are not barred from accessing by law, such as a personal family secret, a business or financial secret, and so on, is referred to as non-public computer information.

Connecting directly to a computer system does not always capture computer data. Data can be acquired through communication links, in the computer system's room, in the building, and from a safe distance. Electromagnetic radiation is constantly present while electronic gadgets are in use.

The stances at the conclusion of the crime are fascinating. According to some scientists, the crime will be over once the information in the computer system has been seized. Another viewpoint considers purposeful access to the system with the intent of getting information to be the conclusion of the crime.

Article 273 of the Criminal Code deals with unauthorized access to a computer system or computer information. There are two components to this article of the Criminal Code: 1) Intentional serious interference with the operation of a computer system by an unauthorized person by entering, transmitting, damaging, deleting, damaging, altering, or blocking computer data; 2) Intentional serious interference with the operation of a computer system by an unauthorized person by entering, transmitting, damaging, deleting, damaging, altering, or blocking computer data, where substantial damage is caused.

This crime is being committed for public relations purposes in order to protect computer data.

As previously said, this offense may be separated into two categories. The objective part of the offense, according to paragraph 1 of article 273, is the intentional destruction, deletion, corruption, modification,

or blockage of computer data by an unauthorized person.

The crucial characteristic of a criminal crime, as Norman's disposition demonstrates, is that the conduct enumerated above do severe injury. "Significant harm" is defined in this section as damage in excess of one thousand manats produced by a socially risky conduct, or other substantial damage to the state's, society's, or individuals' legally protected rights[2].

That is, the infringement is only punishable under Article 273 of the Criminal Code if there is considerable harm.

The crime described in Article 273.1 is one of material character.

The goal part of the offense, according to the second paragraph of article 273, is for an unauthorized person to intentionally substantially interfere with a computer system by inputting, sending, damaging, deleting, corrupting, modifying, or blocking computer information.

Blockage a computer system by input, transmission, damage, deletion, destruction, alteration, or blocking of computer data is a breach of the computer system's regular operation that prohibits or considerably limits the owner's or user's usage of the computer system. The ability to communicate with computer systems.

273-1 is a section of the Criminal Code. Approves the distribution of instruments for committing cybercrime. This crime is divided into three parts: 1) As stated in Articles 271-273 of this Law, the major goal of its preparation or adaption is: manufacturing, import, acquisition, storage, sale, distribution, or acquiring other circumstances for the purpose of committing such offenses (in the case of serious harm); 2) Purchased for storage or use (in case of serious damage) computer passwords, access codes, or other similar information permitting unauthorized access to the computer system or any of its elements for the purpose of committing the offenses described in Articles 271-273 of this Law; 3) Computer passwords, access codes, or other similar data that permits illegal access to the computer system or any portion of it is to establish conditions conducive to the sale, diffusion, or other acquisition of the offenses listed in Articles 271-273 of this Law with the intent to commit a crime;

The target of the crime is public relations, which guarantees that the computer system runs well. Computer programs and devices are known as premedit.

The offence has objective characteristics, according to Article 273-1.1:

a) The manufacture, importation, use, storage, sale, or distribution of devices or computer programs for the purpose of committing the crimes listed in Articles 271-273 of this Law, or other conditions for committing such crimes; b) a socially dangerous consequence, expressed in significant harm, as a result of the listed acts; c) a causal link between the listed acts and the material damage.

The activities described are undertaken with the intent of committing a crime in accordance with Articles 271-273 of the Penal Code, as can be seen from the structure of the article.

General security measures and software protection measures are examples of specific security measures.

It involves obtaining users' information using programs that access a computer system or any element of it, imitate its regular operation, and collect personal interest information from the offending user in a covert manner[5].

The owner can design computer information security software on his own or at his request. In computer software, for example, security tools are frequently utilized. Activities in the field of information security tool design and manufacture are carried out under the terms of an unique agreement[6].

Import refers to introducing the crime's specified substances into the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Acquisition refers to the receiving of devices or computer programs as presents or settlement tools, trading for other products and articles, embezzlement, or any other ownership in violation of the applicable legislation's requirements. Regardless of the mobile application approach, the Republic of Azerbaijan is comprehensible.

Any action aimed at keeping gadgets or computer programs available to you is referred to as maintenance.

Acts aimed at providing devices or computer programs in return for conducting cybercrime are referred to as selling. From the minute it reaches the other person, it is deemed finished.

Distribution through barter with a product other than a sale and other ways is referred to as propagation.

The invention of a range of devices and devices for accessing a computer system, collecting, erasing, destroying, changing, damaging, intercepting data, and adapting ready-made devices for this purpose is known as cybercrime device manufacturing. Actions aiming at ongoing improvement of devices or computer programs are referred to as device or computer program manufacturing.

Distribution through barter with a product other than a sale and other ways is referred to as propagation.

The invention of a range of devices and devices for accessing a computer system, collecting, erasing, destroying, changing, damaging, intercepting data, and adapting ready-made devices for this purpose is known as cybercrime device manufacturing. Actions aiming at ongoing improvement of devices or computer programs are referred to as device or computer program manufacturing.

The criminal's objectively producing computer passwords, access codes, or similar information for the purpose of committing cybercrime, storing, obtaining for use, significant damage resulting from these actions, and the causal relationship between the actions and the damage are all covered by Article 273-1.2.

A computer password (fr. Password-word) is a combination of conventional words or symbols used to confirm identity and authority.

One of the most prevalent forms of assaults against information systems using password or "user-password name" authentication is password hacking. The attack is based on a criminal capturing the password of a user who has access to the system. The attacker likes this approach since it takes over all of the

powers of the user whose account is exposed after successfully supplying the password, while also not raising suspicion among system administrators with the existing account. An attack can take two forms from a technical standpoint[6]:

1) Attempts at direct authentication in the system on many occasions

2) Another method is to analyze the "hashed" form of passwords collected through traffic capture.

Computer access codes are the text of a computer program written in any programming language or in a human-readable sign language, as well as any login information for the transmitter in general.

273-1.3, 271-273 of this Law specify the objective part of the offence. The goal of committing the Articles of Association violations is to establish circumstances for the sale, distribution, or other acquisition of those articles.

The first two forms of crime do significant damage. Significant harm is defined as damage in excess of one thousand manats or to the state's, society's, and individual's legally protected interests.

Falsification of computer information is the final article under the ambit of article 273-2 of the Criminal Code on Cybercrime.

The public threat of crime is exemplified by the fact that putting bogus computer data into a computer system causes the true content of the computer data to be lost, resulting in a disruption of government agencies' and individual companies' regular operations.

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One of the most serious issues in the sphere of cybercrime is the Republic of Azerbaijan's penal legislation in this area, which is still in its infancy. When we all know, as technology advances, new technological

equipment, such as computers with more complex capabilities and other forms of electronic computers, enters the market. As a result of this evolution, new types of cybercrime have emerged, in which individuals violate the rights of actual and legal persons in various ways and break the law in order to further their own goals. In this regard, new criminal acts must be reflected in the Penal Code. On the territory of Azerbaijan, there are also many socially dangerous acts that are not yet included in the cybercrime section, but are penalized under other criminal aspects or do not result in criminal responsibility at all.

The inclusion of crimes committed on the Internet, particularly those aimed at causing damage to other computer systems, in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan would make it easier to combat crime, administer more appropriate and correct sanctions, and carry out rehabilitative work.

Another problem is the lack of sufficient human resources to solve crimes in the field of cyber crimes. Cybercrime is very difficult and requires knowledge in this field. In addition to the spirit of the perpetrator, it is important to know the methods and techniques used in committing this crime.

In my opinion, in addition to raising people who have knowledge in informatics, computers, especially the internet, which is a new type of cybercrime, fraud, vandalism and other areas, judicial officers, inspectors, prosecutors, judges, etc. should be trained on whether cyber crimes have occurred or make decisions that are reasonable enough to justly punish the crimes committed.

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